

INTEGRATION OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO SCHOOLCHILDREN OF SENIOR AGE

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Abstract

The article examines methods and techniques for developing intercultural communication skills in schoolchildren of senior age in the process of learning English. An analysis of the theoretical foundations of intercultural competence is conducted, and practical recommendations for teachers are provided. The importance of integrating the cultural context into the educational process and creating an intercultural environment in the classroom is emphasized.

Key words: intercultural communication, intercultural competence, English language teaching, schoolchildren of senior age, pedagogical strategies.

In the context of globalization and internationalization of the modern world, the ability to interact with representatives of different cultures is becoming increasingly important. The English language, being an international means of communication, plays a key role in the process of developing intercultural skills in students. This article is devoted to the study of methods and techniques aimed at developing intercultural competence in schoolchildren of senior age in the process of teaching English.

Intercultural competence is a set of knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for effective communication and interaction with representatives of other cultures. Its structure includes a cognitive component, including knowledge about the cultures, norms and values of other peoples; an affective component, including the attitude towards representatives of other cultures, the level of tolerance and empathy; a behavioral component, which covers the skills and abilities that allow adequate and effective interaction in an intercultural environment (Waltz, Kuchenmeister, 2007). 913041006

English, being the main language of international communication, contributes to the development of intercultural competence, since the teaching of this language is often accompanied by the study of cultural aspects of English-speaking countries. The inclusion of elements of intercultural communication in the English language program allows pupils not only to improve their language skills, but also to develop the ability for intercultural interaction (Ter-Minasova, 2000). The communicative approach to teaching English focuses on the use of language in real communication situations. Within the framework of this

approach, role-playing games simulating intercultural communication situations and group projects promoting the development of intercultural interaction skills can be used. Authentic materials such as articles, videos, films and songs reflecting the cultural characteristics of English-speaking countries play an important role in the development of intercultural competence. These materials help students immerse themselves in the cultural context and better understand the features of cultural communication (Krasny, 2010).

Interactive methods such as discussions, debates, interactive lectures and seminars promote active participation of students in the educational process and development of their critical thinking. These methods stimulate students to discuss cultural issues and exchange opinions actively. Examples of learning tasks include analyzing cultural differences, studying cultural traditions and customs, and conducting intercultural projects. Analyzing cultural differences involves comparing traditions, customs and norms of behavior of different cultures, which promotes the development of critical analysis skills and the ability to identify cultural differences and similarities. Studying cultural traditions and customs involves preparing and presenting reports on the cultural characteristics of English-speaking countries, which deepens students' knowledge of cultures and develops public speaking skills. Conducting intercultural projects is aimed at creating projects related to the study and presentation of cultural characteristics of different countries, which promotes the development of intercultural interaction skills, the ability to work in a team and critical thinking (Bakhtin, 1975).

Particular attention is paid to developing pupils' tolerant attitudes towards representatives of other cultures, which is an important aspect of intercultural competence. Tolerance implies respect and acceptance of cultural differences, readiness to interact and cooperate with representatives of other cultures. It is important that students not only understand the importance of tolerance, but also demonstrate it in practice in the process of communication and interaction (Ter-Minasova, 2000).

In the process of teaching English to pupils of senior school age, it is important to create conditions for the development of intercultural competence. Teachers should use a variety of methods and approaches so that students can not only master the language, but also learn to understand and respect cultural differences. This includes the use of authentic materials, organizing discussions and debates, as well as the use of role-playing games and modeling situations of intercultural communication.

Authentic materials play a key role in developing intercultural competence. They allow pupils to immerse themselves in the cultural context, become familiar with the cultural traditions and customs of English-speaking countries, and develop critical thinking and analytical skills. The use of films, articles, videos, and songs in English helps students better understand the peculiarities of cultural communication and develop intercultural communication skills (Waltz, Kuchenmeister, 2007).

Thus, the development of intercultural communication skills in pupils of senior school age in the process of learning English is an important task of modern education. The use of a communicative approach, authentic materials and interactive teaching methods contributes to the formation of intercultural competence and the preparation of pupils for effective interaction in the international environment. The effectiveness of these methods is confirmed by the success of completing educational tasks and the level of pupil's participation in the educational process.

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